

THE METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF READING PROFICIENCY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7504431>

ELSEVIER

Mukhitdinova M.R.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi
Doctor of Philosophy
in Pedagogical Science (PhD)

Makhmudova Feruza Salimdjanoyna

Namangan State University
Master's degree student of group 604

Received: 03-01-2023

Accepted: 04-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, o'qish malakasini rivojlantirishning uslubiy tahlili va o'qishni tushunish strategiyalari haqida so'z boradi.

Keywords: mavzular, til (matn) materiali, til materiali, lug'at, grammatika, fonologik minimum.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 03-01-2023

Accepted: 04-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Abstract: В данной статье описываются особенности обучения английскому языку, проводится методический анализ развития навыков чтения и стратегии понимания прочитанного текста..

Keywords: темы, языковой (текстовый) материал, языковой материал, лексика, грамматика, фонологический минимум..

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 03-01-2023

Accepted: 04-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Abstract: This article talks about the features of teaching english also, the methodological analysis of development of reading proficiency and strategies for reading comprehension.

Keywords: topics, language (textual) material, linguistic material, vocabulary, grammar, phonological minima..

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The content of foreign language teaching or what to teach is one of the main problems the Methods deals with. In this chapter an attempt is made to touch on the chief components which, we think, should constitute the content of foreign language teaching in schools; a more detailed consideration will be given in appropriate chapters dealing with teaching various aspects of the language and language skills.

The first component of "what to teach" is habits and skills which pupils should acquire while learning a foreign language. According to the aims of learning this subject they are: hearing (listening comprehension), speaking, reading, and writing. The level of habits and skills is determined by the syllabus for each form. However, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of skills, or the so-called terminal behaviour, is not defined yet for different types of schools and stages of instruction. This is one of the problems for methodologists to investigate and solve.

Nevertheless, some attempts have been made in this respect. Thus in school syllabi we can find some directions as to the level of skills that should be reached in each particular form and their development from form to form. For example, the requirements for hearing and reading skills differ in the 9th and 10th forms. In the 9th form pupils should be able to understand oral language on the basis of the material previously learned and within the topics covered, while in the 10th form the material for hearing should include 1–2 unfamiliar words for pupils to guess their meaning, and to understand a text received by ear, based on the Material learned and on a topic close to those pupils have worked at. This is a new "qualitative step" for pupils in understanding oral language in the 9th form pupils should read with the speed of 1 000 signs per academic hour, in the 10th form the speed of reading is 1 300.

The second component of "what to teach" is language (textual) material, arranged in topics and serving as starting points for the development in oral language and written language, which allows the teacher to reach the practical, educational, and cultural aims set by the syllabus. For example, in the junior stage (the 5th and 6th forms) pupils should speak and read about school, home, town and countryside, nature, physical training and sports. In the senior stage the textual material should cover the following topics: the life of the youth Uzbekistan and abroad; sport in the Uzbekistan and abroad: industry, agriculture, and science in the Uzbekistan and abroad history and geography of the country whose language pupil, study; art and literature in the Uzbekistan and abroad. Topic for speaking and reading are developed from form to form i. e., the pupil's ability to read and speak on a certain (1) language skills: hearing, speaking, reading, and writing as his vocabulary and grammar art topic is widened enriched.

The third component of the content of foreign language teaching is linguistic material, phonology, grammar, and vocabulary carefully selected for the purpose. The selection of linguistic material, the compiling of the so-called minima for instance, minimum vocabulary and minimum grammar has always been one of the most important and difficult problems to be solved and, although a great deal of work has been done in this respect, we are still on the way to its solution

A limited body of linguistic material is required by pupils who have about 600 class hours at their disposal spread over six years (extensive course), and at the same time it must large enough to serve as a sound basis for developing pupils language skills. To sum up what has been said above, the content of foreign language teaching involves:

- (1) Topics
- (2) language (textual) material;
- (3) linguistic material; vocabulary, grammar, phonological minima.

In conclusion it should be said that the content of teaching in our schools is laid down in the syllabus and realized in teaching materials and in the teacher's own speech.

Reading is one of the main skills that a pupil must acquire in the process of mastering a foreign language in school. The syllabus for foreign languages lists reading as one of the leading language activities to be developed. It runs: "To read, without a dictionary, texts containing familiar grammar material and no more than 4–6 unfamiliar words per 100 words of the text the meaning of which, as a rule, should be clear from the context or familiar word-building elements (in the eight-year school). Pupils are to read, with the help of a dictionary, easy texts containing familiar grammar material and 6–8 unfamiliar words per 100 words of the text (in the ten-year school)." Therefore reading is one of the practical aims of teaching a foreign language in schools.

When one says that one can read, it means that one can focus one's attention on the meaning and not on the form; the pupil treats the text as a familiar form of discourse and not as a task of deciphering. "The aim of the teacher is to get his pupils as quickly as possible over the period in which each printed symbol is looked at for its shape, and to arrive at the stage when the pupil looks at words and phrases, for their meaning, almost without noticing the shapes of the separate letters." A good reader does not look at letters, nor even at words, one by one, however quickly; he takes in the meaning of two, three, or four words at a time, in a single moment. The eyes of a very good reader move quickly, taking long "jumps" and making very short "halts". We can call, this ideal reading "reading per se". Reading per se is the end to be attained. It is possible provided:

- (1) the reader can associate the graphic system of the language with the phonic system of that language;
- (2) the reader can find the logical subject and the logical predicate of the sentences:
- (3) the reader can get information from the text (as a whole).

Reading in chorus, reading in groups in imitation of the teacher which is practised in schools forms rather kinesthetic images than graphic ones. The result is that pupils can sound the text but they cannot read. The teacher should observe the rule "Never read words, phrases, sentences by yourself. Give your pupils a chance to read them." For instance, in presenting the words and among them those which are read according to the rule the teacher should make his pupils read these words first. This rule is often violated in school. It is the teacher who first reads a word, a column of words, a sentence, a text and pupils just repeat after the teacher.

In modern textbooks for the 5th form transcription is not used. It is given in the textbooks for the 6th and the 7th forms. Beginning with the 6th and the 7th

forms pupils learn the phonic symbols so that they are able to read unfamiliar words which they look up in the word-list or a dictionary.

All the exercises mentioned above are designed to develop pupils¹ ability to associate the graphic symbols with the phonic ones.

The structural-information exercises are done both in reading aloud and in silent reading. Pupils are taught how to read sentences, paragraphs, texts correctly. Special attention is given to intonation since it is of great importance to the actual division of sentences, to stressing the logical predicate in them. Marking the text occasionally may be helpful.

At an early stage of teaching reading the teacher should read a sentence or a passage to the class himself. When he is sure the pupils understand the passage, he can set individuals and the class to repeat the sentences after him, reading again himself if the pupils' reading is poor.

This kind of elementary reading practice should be carried on for a limited number of lessons only. When a class has advanced far enough to be ready for more independent reading, reading in chorus might be decreased, but not eliminated.

When the pupils have learned to associate written symbols with the sounds they stand for they should read a sentence or a passage by themselves. In this way they get a chance to make use of their knowledge of the rules of reading. It gives the teacher an opportunity to see whether each of his pupils can read. Symbolically it looks like this. Reading aloud as a method of teaching and learning the language should take place in all the forms. This is done with the aim of improving pupils' reading skills.

There are some other ways of correcting pupils' mistakes. The teacher should use them reasonably and choose the one most suitable for the case. Another question arises: whether we should correct a mistake in the process of reading a passage or after finishing it. Both ways are possible. The mistake should be corrected at once while the pupil reads the text if he has made it in a word which will occur two or more times in the text. If the word does not appear again, it is better to let the pupil read the paragraph to the end. Then the mistake is corrected.

A teacher should always be on the alert for the pupils' mistakes, follow their reading and mark their mistakes in pencil.

Silent reading. In learning to read pupils widen their eye span. They can see more than a word, a phrase, a sentence. The eye can move faster than the reader is able to pronounce what he sees. Thus reading aloud becomes an obstacle for perception. It hinders the pupil's comprehension of "the text. It is necessary that the pupil should read silently. Special exercises may be suggested to develop pupils' skills in silent reading. For instance, "Look and say, read and look up." (M. West)

To perform this type of exercises pupils should read a sentence silently, grasp it, and reproduce it without looking into the text. At first they perform such exercises slowly. Gradually the teacher limits the time for the pupils' doing the exercises. It makes them read faster and faster. All this lead to widening their eyespan.

Teaching silent reading is closely connected with two problems:

(1) instructing pupils in finding in sentences what is new in. the information following some structural signals, the latter is possible provided pupils have a certain knowledge of grammar and vocabulary and they can perform lexical and grammar analysis;

(2) developing pupils' ability in guessing.

Pupils should be taught how to find the logical predicate in a sentence. The teacher may ask his pupils to read a text silently and find the words conveying the new information -in the text according to their position. There are some signals which may be helpful in this respect. These are – the Passive Voice (*The doctor was sent for*); the indefinite article (*A man came up to me*); the construction "It is/was" (*It was not difficult for him to finish his work in time*), etc. Grammar and lexical analyses help pupils to assimilate **structural** words, to determine the meaning of a word proceeding from its position in the sentence, to find the meanings of unfamiliar words, and those which seem to be familiar but do not correspond to the structure of the sentence (e. g., / *saw him book a ticket*). Pupils' poor comprehension often results from their poor knowledge of grammar (syntax in particular). The teacher should instruct pupils how to work with a dictionary and a reference book so that they can overcome some difficulties independently. Although in school the teacher often applies grammar and lexical analyses, however, he often does it not with the aim of the "actual division" or parsing of the sentence and better comprehension of the sentence or of the text, but with the aim of checking or revision of his pupils' knowledge of grammar and vocabulary. This does not mean that the teacher should avoid grammar and vocabulary analyses for revision.

The teacher uses mass reading when pupils read sentences, paragraphs of the text silently; the objective may be different: either to widen their eyespan or to find new information. The teacher checks the pupil's silent reading by asking him to reproduce a sentence or a paragraph; through partial reading of a sentence or a clause; through the pupil's interpreting the text; by utilizing true-and-false statements, questions and answers, and, finally, translation.

Pupils perform semantic-communicative exercises reading the text silently. If the work is done during the lesson the teacher uses mass reading. He checks his pupils' comprehension by asking the pupils individually. The techniques the teacher uses to check pupils' ability to get information from the text may be

different. The choice depends on the stage of teaching; on the material used; on pupils' progress.

Unfortunately, some teachers have a tendency to test instead of teach during classroom work and they often confine themselves to reading and translating the text. This is a bad practice. Pupils are tested and not taught. Moreover, the procedure becomes monotonous, and the work is ineffective. A pupil who has been called on to read and received a mark will not usually listen- to his classmates.

The methods and techniques suggested above will help the teacher to teach pupils reading as the syllabus requires.

LITERATURE:

1. Lyaxovitskiy M.V. Metodika prepodavaniya inostrannix yazikov: Uchebnoe posobie. -M.: Visshaya shkola, 1981. -159 s.
2. Metodika obucheniya inostrannim yazikam v sredney shkole: Uchebnik / N.I.Geiz, M.V. Lyaxovitskiy, A.A. Mirolyubov, S.K.Folomkina, S.F. SHatilov. -M.: Visshaya shkola, 1982. -373 s.
3. Metodika prepodavaniya nemetskogo yazika v pedagogicheskom vuze: Iz opita raboti // A.I. Domashnev, K.G. Vazbutskaya, N.N. Zikova, S.F. SHatilov i dr. -M.: Prosvetsenie, 1983. -224 s.
4. Musaev Q. Tarjima nazariyasi asoslari. -T.: Fan, 2005. - 352 b.
5. Obuchenie inostrannomu yaziku kak spetsialnosti: Uchebnoe posobie / M.K. Borodulina, A.L. Karlin, A.S. Lure, A.M. Minina. -2-e izd. ispr. -M.: Visshaya shkola, 1982. -224 s.